

Physiological Synchrony: A Novel Approach to Evaluating User Quality of Experience in Collaborative Distributed Virtual Reality Environments

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Abstract

Synchrony at the physiological level provides an objective measure that can be utilized to examine the collaboration between collaborating partners. When individuals collaborate on a task, their physiological signals can provide valuable insights into their cognitive states, emotions, and overall engagement levels. By analyzing and interpreting these signals synchrony, it becomes possible to gain a deeper understanding of the users' experiences and optimize the collaborative environment accordingly. In our proposed VR system, synchrony from the physiological data of individuals is used to infer the user Quality of Experience (QoE) of collaborators. We propose Physiological Synchrony (PS) of physiological signals as a new method to investigate QoE in a collaborative distributed Virtual Reality immersive environment. We investigate the potential effects of the proposed VR system to support synchrony during remote collaboration, as well as the design guidelines for building such systems.

Keywords: Virtual Reality (VR), Physiological Synchrony (PS), Quality of Experience (QoE).

1 Introduction

Virtual Reality (VR) emerges as a valuable tool for facilitating collaborative tasks in situations where physical proximity is restricted. Immersive VR enables individuals to engage in collaborative activities, such as meetings, conferences, training, and teamwork, while joining from different locations around the globe [Saffo et al., 2021]. Evaluating the Quality of Experience (QoE) of users in immersive VR helps understand how users perceive and experience the environment, which is crucial for assessing the effectiveness and usability of VR platforms [Vlahovic et al., 2022]. With the steady rise in the number of collaboration platforms providing rich interactive experiences like Spatial.io (<https://spatial.io/>), AltspaceVR (<https://altvr.com/>), Facebook Horizon (<https://www.oculus.com/facebook-horizon/>), Mozilla Hubs (<https://hubs.mozilla.com/>), evaluation of QoE of these systems is necessary. However, these systems lack the integration of collecting implicit metrics, which is the primary motivation behind the development. Our prototype VR collaborative system (see Figure 1) solves this problem by collecting eye-tracking data and physiological signals like the heart

Figure 1: Physiological Synchrony in Virtual Reality

rate variability (HRV) and heart rate (HR) to measure physiological synchrony. Our prototype VR collaborative system (see Figure 1) solves this problem by collecting eye-tracking data and physiological signals like the heart

rate, cognitive load, and attention of the collaborators to enable a better mutual understanding. We have proposed a user study with synchrony of physiological signals as an additional metric, for predicting QoE between collaborators. Physiological synchrony serves as an important indicator of QoE in distributed VR collaborative tasks. Inspired by [Dich et al., 2018], we propose to use physiological synchrony as an indicator of collaboration quality, task performance, and learning. By analyzing users’ physiological signals synchrony, researchers can optimize the VR experience, improve communication and collaboration, and ultimately provide a more satisfying QoE in an immersive collaborative VR environment.

2 State of the Art

In the field of evaluating Quality of Experience (QoE) in Social VR, various approaches are employed to capture users’ perceptions, physiological responses, and performance outcomes. Traditionally, user surveys, questionnaires, and interviews utilizing rating scales, open-ended questions, and Likert scales are commonly used to gather subjective feedback on users’ perceptions and overall QoE [Keighrey et al., 2020]. Additionally, physiological measures such as heart rate and skin conductance, along with behavioral indicators like body movements and gaze patterns, provide objective insights into arousal, cognitive load, and engagement levels. Objective measures like task completion time and error rates are utilized to evaluate performance in collaborative tasks. In addition to subjective, physiological, and task performance metrics, we propose the concept of physiological synchrony to evaluate QoE in Social VR. This synchrony metric can provide a better understanding of group Quality of Experience (QoE) in Social VR environments. By measuring synchrony in physiological signals and pupil dilation, a comprehensive understanding of group QoE in Social VR environments can be achieved. Integrating subjective assessments, physiological metrics, objective performance measures, and synchrony analysis offers a multi-faceted evaluation approach, enabling a more nuanced assessment of collaborative experiences and team performance in Social VR.

3 System Implementation

A collaboration VR system inspired by existing systems like Spatial and Mozilla Hubs was developed. Figure 1 shows an overview of our system. Participants on both sides wear the VR headset and E4 wristband. The prototype was built with Unity 3D Game Engine (2019.3.2f1) and tested on two HTC Vive pro eye (<https://www.vive.com/nz/product/vive-pro-eye/overview/>) VR headsets tethered to two Windows 10 computers. An Empatica E4 wristband for each participant. Physiological signals like EDA, HRV, IBI, BVP were obtained from Empatica Real-time cloud to which all data was uploaded from the wristband memory slot. To enable a framework that supports multiple physiological sensors to be integrated seamlessly, several SDKs were integrated as helper classes into Unity to get physiological data from Users. Photon Unity Networking (PUN) SDK with Photon Cloud [12] through the university network provided multi-user features. Eye tracking data was collected from HTC Vive Pro Eye, using Tobi XR SDK and SRanipal SDK. Audio communication was enabled by Photon Voice and was recorded using Audacity for future analysis as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Components used to create the Virtual Collaborative Environment

Collaborative Task Design in Virtual Environment: The VR experience consisted of two users connected to each other virtually. Each participant was in a different physical room in the faculty building and was

Figure 3: Task in Virtual Reality with Leader and Follower Participant

accompanied by either the PI or research assistant during the experiment. During the task, the follower works with the leader, following their commands and giving requested blocks to the leader. The leader must describe the color and shape to the follower. To correctly solve the task, they must move 10 shapes (in a specific order) from one room (where the follower is based) to another room (where the leader is based). In the leader's room, the leader completes the puzzle. Each user is restricted to moving around only in their respective virtual rooms. The follower can pass the objects through the window to the leader as shown in Fig 3. They move around wearing HTC Vive Pro Eye HMD with hand controllers helping them to manipulate the virtual objects with specific keys.

4 User study Evaluation

In our study, we plan to use physiological signals synchrony with pupil dilation synchrony, along with subjective metrics (Presence Questionnaire, SIM-TLX) and task-related metrics (Start time, end time, number of clicks, and number of teleports). In this experiment, there are two groups, one group of Leaders and another group of Followers task role that were shared between the collaborators with factors like Gender, technical expertise, demographics, and familiarity will be considered. In the user study, we would be interested to investigate the following two research questions: 1) Does Physiological Synchrony have any influence on Task performance? 2) How does the physiological synchrony affect groups of similar-gender participants? 3) What are the benefits of grouping experts with no experience users in VR remote collaboration? 4) How do Familiarity and Demographic groups influence synchrony in VR?

- Hypothesis I - Physiological Synchrony of the participant enhances the performance of the remote collaboration system.
- Hypothesis II – Grouping the same gender enhances the synchrony of the remote collaboration system.
- Hypothesis III – Grouping the same experience-level collaborators enhances the synchrony of the remote collaboration system.
- Hypothesis IV – Familiarity with the collaborator enhances the synchrony of the remote collaboration system.

4.1 Experiment Procedure.

The experiment would begin with the participants signing a consent form, answering demographic questions, describing their experience with VR/AR, and familiarity with collaborator. Participants would then be introduced to a short video on navigating the Virtual space and the tasks. At the beginning of the session, all participants completed the consent forms. The E4 was fitted to the wrist of the participant's non-dominant hand in accordance with standard practice [33], [34]. It was verified that the E4 was operating correctly, and 5 minutes of resting time was collected to get the baseline readings of all participants before exposing them to

the virtual environment or putting on the HMD. The HMD was fitted, and participants were provided an opportunity to familiarize themselves with the applications and controls (as part of a training phase in a bespoke training environment). Then, participants progressed to the shared virtual environment and worked together on the shared task. After completion, both E4 and the HMD were collected from the users, and post-questionnaires were given to collect subjective feedback from them.

4.2 QoE Metrics.

We plan to use a within-subject design between the experience of leader and follower roles during a Collaborative VR Task, we conducted an experimental study using a collaborative VR application. I. For each pair of participants, one would be assigned Leader the other will be assigned Follower. The role was randomly allocated one as Leader and the other as Follower. II. We would collect both objective and subjective measures from each condition. The time for completing the tasks would be recorded in a system log file to objectively measure task performance. At the end of each experiment, the participants would be asked to complete subjective questionnaires (from within the VR environment). We would use the questionnaires: SIM TLX [Harris et al., 2020] and Social Presence Questionnaire customized according to the task.

5 Conclusion

A collaborative VR solution that can be integrated with physiological signals synchrony and pupil dilations similarity to enhance the group QoE of collaborative VR applications was presented. Measuring the synchrony of physiological signals of the participants under different grouping conditions was proposed to enhance the QoE of collaborative VR. We plan to provide our findings from development, and user testing in the future.

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References

- [Dich et al., 2018] Dich, Y., Reilly, J., and Schneider, B. (2018). Using physiological synchrony as an indicator of collaboration quality, task performance and learning. In *Artificial Intelligence in Education: 19th International Conference, AIED 2018, London, UK, June 27–30, 2018, Proceedings, Part I 19*, pages 98–110. Springer.
- [Harris et al., 2020] Harris, D., Wilson, M., and Vine, S. (2020). Development and validation of a simulation workload measure: the simulation task load index (sim-tlx). *Virtual Reality*, 24(4):557–566.
- [Keighrey et al., 2020] Keighrey, C., Flynn, R., Murray, S., and Murray, N. (2020). A physiology-based qoe comparison of interactive augmented reality, virtual reality and tablet-based applications. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 23:333–341.
- [Saffo et al., 2021] Saffo, D., Di Bartolomeo, S., Yildirim, C., and Dunne, C. (2021). Remote and collaborative virtual reality experiments via social vr platforms. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 1–15.
- [Vlahovic et al., 2022] Vlahovic, S., Suznjevic, M., and Skorin-Kapov, L. (2022). A survey of challenges and methods for quality of experience assessment of interactive vr applications. *Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces*, 16(3):257–291.